

Anti-tumour Treatment

The prognostic potential of CDX2 in colorectal cancer: Harmonizing biology and clinical practice

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A B S T R A C T

Adjuvant chemotherapy following surgical intervention remains the primary treatment option for patients with localized colorectal cancer (CRC). However, a significant proportion of patients will have an unfavorable outcome after current forms of chemotherapy. While reflecting the increasing complexity of CRC, the clinical application of molecular biomarkers provides information that can be utilized to guide therapeutic strategies. Among these, caudal-related homeobox transcription factor 2 (CDX2) emerges as a biomarker of both prognosis and relapse after therapy. CDX2 is a key transcription factor that controls intestinal fate. Although rarely mutated in CRC, loss of CDX2 expression has been reported mostly in right-sided, microsatellite-unstable tumors and is associated with aggressive carcinomas. The pathological assessment of CDX2 by immunohistochemistry can thus identify patients with high-risk CRC, but the evaluation of CDX2 expression remains challenging in a substantial proportion of patients. In this review, we discuss the roles of CDX2 in homeostasis and CRC and the alterations that lead to protein expression loss. Furthermore, we review the clinical significance of CDX2 assessment, with a particular focus on its current use as a biomarker for pathological evaluation and clinical decision-making. Finally, we attempt to clarify the molecular implications of CDX2 deficiency, ultimately providing insights for a more precise evaluation of CDX2 protein expression.

Introduction

According to the Global Cancer Observatory, colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third-most common cancer type and the second-most cancer-related cause of death worldwide. Clinical management of CRC is guided by the Tumor-Node-metastasis (TNM) AJCC/UICC classification [1–3]. However, about 30 % of CRC patients will experience disease relapse [4].

The use of molecular biomarkers such as microsatellite instability (MSI), BRAF/RAS mutations or HER2 amplification has offered therapeutic alternatives for relapsing patients (reviewed in Sveen et al., 2019 [5]). Recent advances in the field of cancer biology have introduced novel biomarkers that hold promise in revolutionizing prognostication and guide personalized therapeutic decisions. Of note, liquid biopsy has garnered significant attention as it offers a non-invasive method for detecting tumor-secreted proteins and specific mutations from ctDNA

[6–8]. Likewise, the Immunoscore arises as a potent immune-related biomarker of prognosis that can be associated with responses to chemotherapy in CRC [9,10]. Nevertheless, the lack of reliable and straightforward criteria to identify early-stage CRC patients at high risk of recurrence hinders the ability to determine whether the benefits of multi-agent chemotherapy outweigh the risks in terms of disease-specific survival. This fact is mainly due to the inter-patient and intra-tumoral heterogeneity of CRC, which poses a challenge for the discovery of novel predictive biomarkers to be leveraged for clinical decision-making [11].

In this context, the reduced expression of caudal-related homeobox 2 (CDX2), a master regulator of intestinal differentiation and a marker of CRC cells, identifies a small subgroup of patients with a particularly poor outcome [7,12,13]. The loss of CDX2 protein expression can be detected by routine histopathological screening [13]. Unfortunately, patient segregation according to CDX2 positivity is often limited due to its intra-

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tumoral expression heterogeneity [13], and the underlying biological mechanisms remain to be elucidated.

In this review, we bring together the biology of CDX2 and its clinical implications, with the intention of rationalizing the open questions concerning the use of CDX2 as a biomarker of CRC outcome. On the one hand, we revisit the roles of CDX2 in intestinal development, homeostasis, and CRC. On the other hand, we review the state-of-the-art clinical use of CDX2 and its predictive power.

CDX2 structure and homologs

The caudal-related homeobox (Cdx) protein family belongs to the ParaHox gene cluster, which shares ancestry with the Hox gene cluster [14]. The Caudal gene was first described in *Drosophila* [15], and homologs have been described since then in several species, including *Xenopus*, chicken, mice, hamsters, and humans [16–21]. In mammals, the Cdx family comprises three members: Cdx1, Cdx2, and Cdx4 [22–26].

CDX2 contains a highly conserved DNA-binding homeodomain, with a particular affinity for CpG-methylated dinucleotides and optimal binding for CAATAAA and TCGTAAA sequences [18,22,27,28]. This homeodomain is nearly identical to that of CDX1, resulting in overlapping functions throughout intestinal development [22,29]. Additionally, CDX2 contains an activation domain harboring a phosphorylation site at serine 60 [30]. Interestingly, CDX2 can be phosphorylated through two different members of the MAPK family, p38 or MEK, which leads to a post-translational regulation of CDX2 activity [30,31].

CDX2 in intestinal homeostasis

CDX2 during intestinal specification

Intestinal development is a tightly regulated process that requires the controlled expression of numerous gene products through time and space. Like many genes belonging to the Hox and ParaHox clusters, the expression of Cdx1, Cdx2, and Cdx4 throughout embryonic development has been extensively characterized [17,18,32]. Although the role of Cdx4 is still poorly understood, Cdx1 and Cdx2 have crucial and overlapping roles for posterior specification and axial elongation during embryogenesis [29,33–37]. In particular, Cdx2 first determines trophoderm differentiation in 8-to-32-cell zygotes [38–40]. In later stages, its expression becomes restricted to the midgut and hindgut endoderm, ultimately leading to the formation of the intestinal epithelium [41,42].

Genetic ablation experiments have demonstrated a key role of CDX2 but not CDX1 in intestinal cell fate specification during embryonic development [43,44]. Cdx2^{-/-} cells in chimeric mice developed polypoid lesions with a forestomach differentiation pattern [45]. Indeed, Foxa3- and Villin-driven conditional ablation of Cdx2 in the developing gut of mice resulted in the loss of intestinal architecture, the ectopic proliferation of keratinocytes, and a foregut differentiation [46–48]. Concomitant with the formation of stomach-like structures, Cdx2^{-/-} intestinal cells expressed Sox2, whose expression is restricted to the foregut and determines gastric differentiation [46,47,49,50]. These results are further supported by *in vitro* and *in silico* analyses using organoid technology, ATAC-/ChIP-seq, and single cell RNA sequencing data, where the ability of CDX2 to bind its targets follows dynamic chromatin changes throughout embryonic development. The coordination between chromatin opening and CDX2 transcriptional regulation results in the establishment of a regional identity in both intestinal epithelial and mesenchymal progenitors, which can be altered towards a foregut-like specification after genetic ablation of CDX2 [51–54]. Furthermore, the reprogramming of either endothelial or mesenchymal cells with a combination of transcription factors that include CDX2 is sufficient to produce organoids with intestinal epithelium fate [55].

In adults, CDX2 protein expression is restricted to the epithelium of the gastrointestinal tract and the appendix. It spans from the beginning of the duodenum and increases gradually throughout the small intestine, reaching its maximum at the ileum and the proximal colon. In contrast, CDX2 expression becomes weaker throughout the colon and is completely absent in the distal colon [17,37].

The CDX2 regulatory network

In homeostasis, CDX2 acts as a master regulator of specific genes controlling intestinal identity and enterocyte maturation by regulating the expression of target genes associated with differentiated cell types in the epithelium (Fig. 1) [46,56,57]. A vast body of research has highlighted sucrose isomaltase (SI), carbonic anhydrase 1 (CA1) and mucin-2 (MUC2) as the main target genes of CDX2 [41,58–61], together with other specific genes such as CDX1, ISX, HNF1 α and HNF4 α , KLF4, Guanyl cyclase G, Cadherin-17, Claudin-2 (CLDN2) and Ephrin B1 [18,42,46,62,63]. *In vivo* deletion of CDX2 in the villi is associated with a downregulation of these targets and leads to a lethal impairment of intestinal morphology due to the loss of differentiated cell types, including enterocytes and goblet cells. Accordingly, the overexpression of CDX2 triggers premature maturation of intestinal cells and a reduction of Paneth cells [48,64,65].

Owing to its paramount role in intestinal identity, CDX2 activity is tightly regulated by co-factors with the ability to either stimulate or repress CDX2 activity. In particular, HNF1 α , HNF4 α , GATA4, GATA6, TCF4, and β -catenin have been found to synergistically enhance CDX2 transcriptional activity in the intestine [49,60,65–67]. When expressed ectopically, HNF4 α , GATA6, TCF4, and β -catenin can activate CDX2 expression in non-intestinal cells [49]. More recently, CDX2 and HNF4 α have been found to be regulated by SATB2 in stem cells to sustain the expression of colonic genes, and loss of SATB2 induces an ileum-like conversion [68]. Conversely, SOX2 and SOX9 can repress CDX2 activity. First, SOX2 represses CDX2 expression to maintain gastric specification and antagonizes the activity of TCF4/ β -catenin. Second, SOX9 is responsible for the reduction of CDX2 expression in Paneth cells, blunting the effect of HNF4 α /GATA6 at the bottom of the crypt [49,64,69].

In addition to its role in intestinal cell differentiation, CDX2 is required to maintain the integrity of the intestine. CDX2 expression regulates the establishment of tight junctions between epithelial cells and a protective barrier against pathogens through the expression of cadherins, CLDN2 and MUC2, and regulates cell trafficking and polarity through RAB11A and KIF3B [41,70].

Indeed, CDX2 deficiency results in defective barrier functions, atrophy of the microvilli of enterocytes, and impaired endolysosomal transport (Fig. 1) [67,70,71]. Furthermore, CDX2 has been found to participate in iron transport through the regulation of Hephastin (HEPH) [72]. In accordance with these observations, the reduced CDX2 expression in heterozygous Cdx2 ^{+/-} mice was associated with greater intestinal permeability and hypersensitivity to experimentally induced intestinal inflammation [73].

More recent research has highlighted additional roles of CDX2 in preventing inflammatory diseases in the intestine, such as inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and ulcerative colitis (UC). CDX2 regulates the transcription of TRIM31, which is a negative regulator of the NLRP3 inflammasome, MEP1A, LAMC2, and H2-T3 [74–77]. These CDX2-dependent factors are impaired in UC and IBD, and their loss is associated with an elevated infiltration of inflammatory macrophages and increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α (Fig. 1) [74–77].

CDX2 in stemness, proliferation and differentiation

The architecture of the intestinal epithelium has been extensively studied, and it mainly consists of three well-defined compartments

Fig. 1. CDX2 roles in intestinal homeostasis. CDX2 regulates a transcriptional program driving intestinal cell differentiation (upper left blue section). The lower orange section summarizes the negative impact of CDX2 loss in the epithelium, highlighting its crucial role in maintaining intestinal functions and integrity, as well as preventing inflammatory diseases. ISC: intestinal stem cell.

organized into crypts and villi: (1) a stem cell zone located at the crypt base, (2) a transit amplifying compartment that includes rapidly proliferating lineage-committed cells, and (3) a zone of mature epithelial cells that migrate toward the tip of the villi. A dynamic renewal of the epithelium is fueled by a constant expansion of new progenitors and the apoptosis of mature cells at the villi tips [78]. Despite its nature as a differentiation marker, intestinal stem cells (ISCs) and differentiated cells express similar levels of CDX2 mRNA, and protein expression can be found in all three intestinal compartments as detected by immunohistochemistry, with the exception of a faint expression in Paneth cells, where CDX2 is repressed by SOX9 [64,65,69,79–81]. In this line, lineage tracing experiments using CDX2P-CreER^{T2} showed random EYFP labeling within colonic crypts immediately after a single dose of tamoxifen, and CDX2-EYFP + ISCs gave rise to every cell type, eventually

repopulating entire crypts [80]. Coinciding with these observations, conditional deletion of CDX2 can be achieved in all intestinal cells using Villin-CreER^{T2} mice, leading to morphogenic aberrations and intestinal insufficiency [47,52,76]. More specifically, when CDX2 deletion occurred in ISCs using LGR5-CreER^{T2} mice, stem cells failed to generate any differentiated cell type and organized into slow-cycling cystic structures [81].

These data evidence multiple roles for CDX2 depending on the intestinal cell type. On the one hand, the formation of undifferentiated cystic structures in the absence of CDX2 in LGR5 + cells suggests a prominent role during cell fate commitment in ISCs [81]. Alternatively, although the Villin-CreER^{T2} mouse model targeted virtually every intestinal cell type in the crypts, the abnormal intestinal phenotypes could be caused by malabsorption in enterocytes and/or differentiation into

more anterior lineages, which suggests that CDX2 in differentiated cells maintains their cellular functions and intestinal identity [46–48,51,67]. This functional duality is context-dependent and can be explained by chromatin changes in CDX2-binding regulatory regions and co-occupancies with different cofactors [65–67,82,83], a phenomenon that resembles the chromatin accessibility patterns throughout development and gut specification [52,54]. Likewise, phosphorylation by MEK or p38 may impose another layer of CDX2 post-translational regulation in homeostasis [30,31].

On the other hand, CDX2 ablation markedly decreases the number of proliferating cells in the crypt base, suggesting direct roles in controlling ISC proliferation [64,65,67,81]. However, how CDX2 regulates proliferation in committed cell types is still unclear. For instance, two independent works from the laboratory of Ramesh A. Shivdasani suggest that CDX2 loss has no impact on the number of proliferating cells from the transit amplifying and differentiated compartments [65,81], while Grainger and colleagues showed more KI67+ cells in those compartments after CDX2 conditional ablation, which agrees with the direct transcriptional regulation by CDX2 of p21, a repressor of the cell cycle, through which CDX2 inhibits proliferation in colon cancer cells [47,84,85]. The fact that the Villin-CreER^{T2} mouse model targets ISCs and differentiated cells indistinctly could explain the disparity of both perspectives and makes it challenging to extract conclusions on how CDX2 regulates mature intestinal cells.

The molecular landscape of CDX2 in colorectal cancer

The loss of CDX2: Genetic and epigenetic alterations

As further discussed in this review, while CDX2 is usually expressed uniformly in CRC cells and its expression is consistently retained during metastasis [86], a relatively small proportion of tumors display a loss in CDX2 expression [7,12,13,87–90]. Paradoxically, inactivating mutations in the CDX2 gene are highly uncommon in CRC, with a frequency of 1.3% based on information from multiple publications and TCGA databases [91]. Among the multiple mutations identified in CDX2, the V306Cfs2 mutation is the most frequent, while other variants such as Q250X, A239V, and N308S were each found in no more than one patient [91], and a study conducted in Memorial Sloan Kettering failed to identify any mutations of CDX2 in CRC [92]. This low mutational occurrence suggests that epigenetic mechanisms, rather than genomic alterations, could explain the observed loss of CDX2 expression in CRC patients (Fig. 2) [12].

Indeed, promoter methylation of CDX2 has been associated with a decreased gene expression and increased risk of CRC [83]. In particular, Kawai and colleagues reported two CpG-rich sites in the CDX2 promoter, located at –1570 to –1200 and –220 to +880 respectively [85]. Methylation occurring at the –220 to +880 locus is associated with decreased CDX2 expression, which can be recovered when methylated CRC cell lines are treated with the DNA methyltransferase inhibitors [83,85]. Additionally, Graule and colleagues demonstrated that histone deacetylation by HDAC4 and HDAC5 can further repress CDX2 expression, which can be reverted by HDAC inhibitors [83]. Although more

Fig. 2. CDX2 loss in CRC. The loss of CDX2 is mainly driven by epigenetic alterations such as methylation and histone deacetylation in the CDX2 promoter region. CDX2-negative tumors are associated with clinicopathological features (upper right blue box) of aggressive CRC. The loss of CDX2 in tumors is closely associated with classically altered pathways of CRC, such as WNT, MAPK and TGF-beta, as well as an increased stromal infiltration (lower left orange box). EMT: epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition; ECM: extra-cellular matrix; dMMR: deficient mismatch repair; CMS: consensus molecular subtype.

research is needed to fully understand the epigenetic mechanisms regulating CDX2 expression in CRC, these data opens therapeutic possibilities using inhibitors of DNA methyltransferases and histone deacetylases to restore CDX2 expression in cancer cells.

The impact of CDX2 loss on hallmark pathways of CRC

Despite the intricate heterogeneity of mutational events, a vast body of research has identified fundamental molecular pathways that are affected during the evolution of most colorectal carcinomas, such as MAPK, Wnt, and TGF-beta [3,91,93,94]. On account of its central role in intestinal homeostasis, CDX2 closely interacts with key factors participating in these signaling cascades, which ultimately impose a tight regulation of the cell cycle. In this line, the loss of CDX2 not only impacts proliferation by directly downregulating p21 expression [47,84], but also through the dysregulation of these pathways (Fig. 2).

The ability of MEK and p38 to phosphorylate CDX2 suggests a close interaction between the ERK/MAPK and p38/MAPK pathways and CDX2 activity. Indeed, mutations in these pathways trigger a constitutive activation of the MAPK signaling cascade that leads to a decreased CDX2 expression, which consequently enhances epithelial cell proliferation and stemness [95,96]. Of note, BRAF can regulate CDX2 expression both at the transcriptional and protein levels, and the BRAF^{V600E} mutated variant represses differentiation and promotes cell proliferation through direct downregulation of CDX2 [97,98]. In agreement, loss of CDX2 is typically associated with BRAF^{V600E} mutated tumors in CRC patients [97,99–101].

In more than 85 % of colorectal carcinomas, mutations in the tumor suppressor APC lead to permanent activation of the Wnt pathway [3,91,93,94]. Alternatively, the loss of CDX2 may also exert an influence on the Wnt signaling cascade in CRC. In this context, CDX2 interacts with WNT pathway components in homeostasis. For instance, WNT ligands in the stem cell niche enhance CDX2 expression through nuclear translocation and DNA binding of the TCF4/β-catenin complex [49,66,78,83,102]. In turn, CDX2 up-regulation leads to β-catenin degradation through the transactivation of GSK-3β and transcriptional regulation of APC and AXIN2. This negative feedback loop suggests a tight regulation of ISC identity and division, and the loss of CDX2 leads to increased WNT signaling, abnormal cell proliferation, and metastatic dissemination in the liver [85,103–105].

Colorectal carcinomas may also accumulate inactivating mutations in factors within the TGF-beta signaling cascade, such as SMAD proteins and TGF-beta Receptor II [3,91,93,94]. A few studies have reported an association between CDX2 expression and the TGF-beta pathway, albeit with opposing effects. For instance, CDX2 may interact with SMAD2, SMAD3 and SMAD4, leading to a functional amplification, but it may also decrease the expression of TGF-beta ligands by epithelial cells [73,106–108]. Additionally, recent reports have shown that CDX2 expression represses epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT), which is mainly regulated by TGF-beta signaling. Therefore, the loss of CDX2 leads to increased EMT and migratory features of CRC epithelial cells [109,110]. Nevertheless, how the loss of CDX2 impacts the TGF-beta pathway of tumor cells is yet to be elucidated.

Clinical significance of CDX2 loss

CDX2 as a clinical marker of CRC

Since CRC cells commonly express CDX2 [71], the evaluation and quantification of its protein levels by immunohistochemistry (IHC) on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tumor sections is a valuable and well-established technique in routine diagnostic practice. Yet, CDX2 is not exclusively expressed by CRC cells, as a large fraction of different gastrointestinal neoplasms may also exhibit CDX2-positive nuclei. For instance, CDX2 + cancer cells are detected in duodenal (100 %), gastric (71 %) and pancreatic adenocarcinomas (30 %) [111,112]. Likewise,

CDX2 can also be expressed in malignancies other than adenocarcinomas such as neuroendocrine tumors, which are characterized by a diffuse CDX2 nuclear positivity [113]. While CDX2 expression is commonly nuclear, positive events can also be detected outside of the nuclei of cells. For example, cytoplasmic granular CDX2 immunoreactivity has been associated with the production of squamous morules in tumors from different organs (e.g. thyroid, lung, stomach, gallbladder, endometrium and ovary) as well as mucosal inflammation in Barrett’s esophagus [114,115].

Generally, CDX2 nuclear detection alone is thought to be a helpful indication of colorectal origin when defining metastases of uncertain cause [111]. However, and in view of its broad expression, current guidelines recommend the evaluation of cytokeratin (CK) 20 and 7 in addition to CDX2 protein expression to determine the colorectal origin of particular metastases. Indeed, CK20+/CK7-/CDX2 + cancer cells are present in approximately 80 % of metastasis originated from colorectal adenocarcinomas [111,116]. However, the efficacy of CK20/CK7/CDX2 evaluation is limited to microsatellite stable cancers, as microsatellite unstable tumors frequently exhibit aberrant elevated CK7, decreased CK20, and loss of CDX2 expression [12,116,117].

Besides pathological assessment by IHC, detection of circulating tumor cells (CTCs) in liquid biopsies from patients with metastatic CRC can be leveraged as a strong independent prognostic marker of progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) [118,119]. In this direction, and given its expression specificity, it has been demonstrated that CDX2 can be included in immunofluorescence panels to discriminate CTCs of colorectal origin, and that the number of CDX2 + CTCs is correlated with clinical-histopathological factors, such as TNM stage and lymph node status [120–124].

Limitations of the pathological assessment of CDX2

Noteworthy, there exists a wide variability in reported CDX2 negative cases, ranging from 5 % to 30 % depending on the study (summarized in Table 1) [7,12,13,87–90,125]. This percentual fluctuation could be explained by patient demographics, as a higher proportion of CDX2 loss has been reported in more advanced CRC stages [125]. Another relevant cause of variation is the lack of consistency in scoring standards and cut off points; there is indeed no consensus criterion for distinguishing CDX2 positive from negative cases [61]. When CDX2 expression loss is defined as the proportion of cancer cells with a total

Table 1

The variability in CDX2 negative tumor assessment. DFS: disease-free survival, MSS: microsatellite stable, CRC: colorectal cancer, NA: non-applicable.

	Detection method	CDX2 (-) (%)	Patients (n) CDX2 (-) / total	Independent DFS predictor	Ref.
Tarazona et al., 2020	protein	5,3	8 / 150	yes	[7]
Bae et al., 2015	protein	5,9	42 / 713	yes	[12]
Dalerba et al., 2016	mRNA mRNA	4,1 6,9	87 / 2115 32 / 466	NA yes	[13]
Slik et al., 2019	protein protein	12,1 10,9	38 / 314 25 / 232	yes in MSS CRC	[87]
Konukiewitz et al., 2021	protein	10,0	102 / 1003	no	[88]
Graule et al., 2018	protein	6,0	39 / 637	yes	[89]
Pilati et al., 2017	mRNA	15,6	73 / 469	yes	[90]
Baba et al., 2009	protein	29,0	183 / 621	in familial CRC	[125]
Hansen et al., 2018	protein protein	11.6 8.5	66 / 571 50 / 586	in combined cohort	[126]

lack of staining regardless of intensity, CDX2 negative tumors may be defined as those with a complete lack of expression in all cancer cells (Fig. 3) [125]. Several studies, on the other hand, report the use of cut off criterion ranging from 40 to 100 % of CDX2 negative cells [12,88,89,126], thus indicating that even a subset of CDX2 negative clones may have a significant impact on the whole tumor behavior (Fig. 3). As a result, despite the fact that the association between CDX2 loss/decreased expression and a worse prognosis in CRC is well documented [127,128], the clinical utility of CDX2 as a prognostic factor remains rather limited.

To address this issue, Dalerba and colleagues suggested an original four-tiered method based on both the CDX2 expression intensity and the percentage (majority vs minority) of CDX2 positive cancer cells [13]. In this setting, tumors with a total lack of staining (score 0) and tumors with mild staining in a minority of cancer cells (score 0.5) are classified as CDX2 negative. Conversely, tumors exhibiting moderate to strong staining in all cancer cells (score 3) or in the majority of the cancer cells (score 2) are considered CDX2 positive [13]. Importantly, several intermediate scenarios are still excluded from this scoring system. For example, tumors with convincing focal or dispersed loss to weak CDX2 expression in a landscape of moderate to strong CDX2 positive cancer cells as well as tumors with only weak staining in most cancer cells are considered non-evaluable (Fig. 3) [13]. Collectively, these findings indicate that incorporating CDX2 assessment into clinical practice may necessitate the development of a consensus scoring that better considers the intra-tumoral heterogeneity of CRC cells.

The clinical prognostic value of CDX2

As highlighted in the previous section, CDX2-negative cases in CRC constitute a relatively small proportion of the population [7,12,13,87–90]. Yet, CDX2-negative tumors exhibit significant enrichment in various characteristics, including defective DNA mismatch repair (MMR) tumors, proximal tumor location, BRAF-mutated tumors, poor differentiation, vascular invasion, and CpG island methylated phenotype [12,117,125,129]. These characteristics associated with the loss of CDX2 expression reflect the aggressive phenotype of this subgroup of patients (Fig. 2).

In this line, multiple studies conducted in recent years have

consistently shown that the absence of CDX2 expression correlates with poorer disease-free survival (DFS) outcomes. These findings highlight the significance of CDX2 as a prognostic marker in various contexts and underscore its potential clinical implications in assessing patient prognosis [7,13,90]. Although there may be discrepancies in certain studies [7], so far, both the stage II and stage III CRC patients harboring CDX2-negative tumors have exhibited a higher rate of DFS when receiving adjuvant chemotherapy [13].

Association of CDX2 with the consensus molecular subtypes of CRC

The molecular classification of CRC, based on gene expression profiling, has provided insights into specific altered biological pathways within the four Consensus Molecular Subtypes (CMS) [130]. In this regard, some studies have identified a significant proportion of CDX2-negative patients (94 %) classified into two CMS subgroups, namely, CMS1, characterized by microsatellite instability (MSI), immune infiltration, and a favorable prognosis; and CMS4, exhibiting a mesenchymal/stem cell phenotype and a poorer prognosis (Fig. 2) [7,90]. Of note, both of these groups have been associated with a phenotype resembling sessile serrated adenomas and activation of the TGF-beta pathway, which is particularly prominent in CMS4 [130]. In contrast, the proportion of CDX2-negative CRC in the other CMS groups was relatively low, comprising only 0.5 % in CMS2 and 5.6 % in CMS3 [7,90]. Consequently, CDX2 protein levels assessed by IHC can thus be used to exclude the stromal subtypes CMS1/4 [131].

The loss of CDX2 expression was associated with poorer DFS in both the CMS1 and CMS4 groups in one cohort [7]. However, in another cohort, the loss of CDX2 correlated with a worse prognosis among CMS4 patients but not CMS1 [90]. These conflicting results may be attributed to the evaluation of CDX2 expression at the RNA level in one instance [90] and at the protein level in the other [7].

Collectively, these findings shed light on the distinct molecular characteristics and pathways implicated in these specific CMS subgroups, further advancing our understanding of the heterogeneity of CRC. Remarkably, even when considering the CMS groups, CDX2 expression retains its independent prognostic. This underscores the robustness of CDX2 as a prognostic marker, irrespective of the molecular subtypes defined by the CMS classification.

Fig. 3. Representative epithelial cancer cell-specific CDX2 immunostaining in CRC patients. Left panel: CDX2 positive tumor. Center panels: tumors with heterogeneous CDX2 expression. Right panel: CDX2 negative tumor. Black arrows point to CDX2 (-) epithelial cancer cells. White arrows point to CDX2 (+) epithelial cancer cells. Scale bars: 200 μ m.

Modulation of CDX2 expression by the tumor microenvironment

The heterogeneity of colorectal tumors is not limited to the mutational landscape of epithelial cancer cells, but also includes a variety of stromal and immune infiltrates that exert a relevant impact on cancer progression and therapeutic outcomes. Such influence of the tumor microenvironment (TME) is reflected in the CMS1 and CMS4 subtypes of CRC, and their association with the loss of CDX2 that suggests a modulation of CDX2 protein expression by stromal cues. On the one hand, recent reports show a link between CDX2 expression and tumor infiltration, which parallels the role of CDX2 in preventing intestinal inflammation during homeostasis. Of note, the loss of CDX2 is associated with higher levels of tumor-infiltrating macrophages [77,110,132]. Mechanistically, the work of Chewchuk and colleagues has identified the histocompatibility complex protein H2-T3, which encodes for a protein of the major histocompatibility complex class I (MHC-I), as a direct target of CDX2. H2-T3 expression regulates macrophage infiltration through the activity of intestinal iCD8 α lymphocytes. Therefore, the loss of CDX2 results in the downregulation of H2-T3, consequently leading to increasing numbers of macrophages [77]. Further research should shed light on novel immune-related roles of CDX2 in CRC and how CDX2 expression might be regulated by the type and density of immune infiltrates.

On the other hand, several reports from the laboratory of Jean-Noel Freund have identified cancer-associated fibroblasts and components of the extracellular matrix (ECM) [133–135], both of which are particularly abundant in CMS4 tumors [130], as mediators of CDX2 expression in cancer cells. In vivo engraftment of CRC cell lines has shown that the expression of CDX2 from the injected tumor cells can be severely altered depending on whether they are implanted subcutaneously or in the caecum of mice [133]. This phenomenon suggests a strong environment-related dependence of CDX2 expression, possibly explained by differential collagen-induced β -integrin signaling or the secretion of fibroblast-derived factors such as WNT5A. Interestingly, in a mosaic mouse model for CDX2 genetic ablation in an APC^{+/Δ14} background, epithelial cells devoid of CDX2 modified the TME through the secretion of ECM components, chemokines, and cytokines, leading to the formation of dysplastic lesions by decreasing CDX2 expression in APC^{+/Δ14} cells [135]. Therefore, the loss of CDX2 can further affect CDX2 expression in neighboring cells through direct alterations of the tumor stroma.

Concluding remarks

Trying to solve the CDX2 conundrum: TME and epigenetic modulation

As stated above, the main limitation of CDX2-based CRC patient stratification is reduced to the protein expression heterogeneity in those cases where CDX2 is not entirely lost [7,12,13,87–90,125,126]. In this scenario, the issue remains whether a relatively small proportion of CDX2-negative tumor cells is enough to confer the whole tumor mass with features of CDX2-lost CRC. Indeed, the work of Balbinot and colleagues suggests that a reduced proportion of CDX2 negative cancer cell clones could trigger a stromal transformation, which subsequently induces a CDX2 expression shutdown in wild-type cells [135]. From these observations, it could be extrapolated that the stromal composition in those regions with evident loss of CDX2 could be distinct from the one surrounding cancer cells with fully functional CDX2 expression. Given the vast intra-tumoral and inter-patient TME heterogeneity in CRC, distinct subpopulations or transcriptional states of CAFs and/or immune cells could be associated with changes in CDX2 expression [136,137]. In this context, recent evidence has shown that standard-of-care chemotherapy can induce a profound transformation of the TME [138,139], which could ultimately alter the CDX2 expression of resistant cancer cells.

This stromal influence could further support the notion that

epigenetic alterations, rather than mutational events, modulate CDX2 expression in cancer cells. Indeed, there is evidence supporting that epigenetic changes occurring in cancer cells can be induced by cells of the TME. For instance, two independent publications demonstrate how breast and prostate cancer cells enter epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition through CAFs-induced promoter methylation [140,141]. Additionally, inflammation can also lead to DNA methylation in epithelial cells, which ultimately leads to enhanced tumorigenesis [142–144].

In conclusion, CDX2 expression and the TME may establish a bidirectional communication that can lead to CRC progression. This non-cell-autonomous regulation may explain the varying CDX2 protein expression observed in some CRC patients and could determine the extent to which CDX2-negative cancer cells impact the overall tumor behavior.

Future perspectives

Evaluating CDX2 expression has the potential to provide a more individualized and well-informed strategy for patient care across diverse clinical contexts, including those that may be subject to controversy in CRC treatment. For instance, it could enable optimization of patient outcomes by considering CDX2 alongside other clinicopathological features, which might result in refining combination therapies and a better selection of candidates for clinical trials. Given that CDX2 expression has been associated with therapeutic responses [101], it holds the potential to guide the choice between chemotherapy, targeted therapy and/or immunotherapy while sparing unnecessary side effects. In this direction, several studies including the IDEA trial are investigating whether adjuvant chemotherapy can be reduced to minimize detrimental side effects while maintaining or even improving therapeutic outcome [10,145–147]. While there is no evidence on biomarkers predicting a reduced benefit from shortened adjuvant chemotherapy, plasma detection and monitorization of CDX2 expression through multiple liquid biopsies offers a tool to modulate treatment duration [7,148]. With this intention, clinical trials such as DYNAMIC [149] and PEGASUS (NCT04259944, ongoing) are evaluating the feasibility of liquid biopsy for a continuous monitorization of patient outcome, which allows therapeutic modulation according to real-time disease progression.

Since a pathological assessment by IHC alone may be insufficient, the precise evaluation of CDX2 expression warrants for complementary molecular approaches. Given the rare occurrence of mutational events, examining methylated and acetylated regions of CDX2 promoters offer promising insights into cases with lower CDX2 expression and, hence, a poor clinical outcome. In this direction, the combination of epigenetic data with CDX2 protein staining by IHC could untangle the ambiguity surrounding mixed CDX2 expression in CRC, and epigenetic drugs could be leveraged to reverse its loss in tumors.

In the context of intra-tumor heterogeneity, further research ought to explore the nature of those stromal subpopulations that might modulate CDX2 expression in tumor cells. As a result, specific markers of CAFs/immune subpopulations could be leveraged for a more precise patient stratification according to CDX2 activity, with a particular interest in patients who relapsed after chemotherapy.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

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